

Identity Management for Enhanced Security in Industrial Automation and Control Systems

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Abstract—This paper explores the integration of blockchain-based Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) technologies into Industrial Automation and Control Systems (IACS) to strengthen cybersecurity and operational resilience. After an overview of the threats facing industrial systems, we present a logical framework for a layered defense incorporating SSI. The logical framework for integrating SSI into existing industrial automation reference architectures provides a detailed examination of multi-layered endpoint protection strategies that leverage SSI to improve security. The framework takes into account the requirements for authentication, authorization and secure communication in different industrial contexts. Key use cases illustrate the practical applications of blockchain-based SSI, including secure maintenance workstations, inter-zone communication interlocks, convenience ports, security networks and remote user authentication. These use cases demonstrate how SSI increases both security and efficiency in IACS environments. The paper concludes with insights into the integration aspects and transformative potential of blockchain-based SSI for industrial security.

Index Terms—SSI, Blockchain, industrial networks, 6G

I. INTRODUCTION

Industrial Automation and Control Systems (IACS) play a central role in modern critical infrastructure, spanning sectors such as manufacturing, energy, transportation, and utilities. With the adoption of Industry 4.0 principles and increasing convergence of IT and OT networks, these systems are becoming more interconnected, intelligent, and data-driven. While this evolution enables greater efficiency and flexibility, it also introduces new cybersecurity challenges, particularly around identity and trust management.

Traditional security strategies in industrial environments often rely on perimeter-based defenses and isolated network zones. However, such models are no longer sufficient in the face of advanced persistent threats, insider attacks, and sophisticated malware that exploit gaps in authentication and access control. One widely adopted paradigm—Defense in Depth—introduces multiple layers of security across physical, network, and software domains to reduce the attack surface [1]. Yet, even within this layered model, identity remains an underdeveloped component. Devices, users, and applications are often authenticated through static credentials or centralized systems, creating single points of failure and limited visibility.

In this context, Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI)—a decentralized identity management model based on blockchain tech-

nologies—offers a promising alternative. SSI allows users and devices to own, control, and present their verifiable credentials without relying on a central authority [2], [3]. When embedded into IACS environments, SSI can enhance security through cryptographic authentication, fine-grained access control, and immutable audit trails [4]. Its distributed nature also aligns well with the decentralized topology of modern industrial networks and supports zero-trust principles, where no entity is implicitly trusted.

This paper proposes a comprehensive framework for integrating blockchain-based SSI into IACS, enhancing the traditional Defense in Depth model by introducing an explicit identity layer. Leveraging the Purdue Enterprise Reference Architecture (PERA) as a foundation [5], we outline how SSI can be systematically embedded across different industrial zones and levels—ranging from enterprise planning systems to safety-critical controllers. We present a series of representative use cases that illustrate the practical benefits of this integration, including secure maintenance operations, authenticated cross-zone communications, controlled access via convenience ports, and verified interactions with remote users. By incorporating SSI into industrial security architectures, we aim to bridge the gap between robust identity management and operational requirements, enabling more resilient, secure, and efficient IACS networks.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section II reviews key background concepts, including threat models and the logical security framework for IACS. Section III introduces the role of blockchain-based SSI in OT environments, including its technical properties and advantages. Section IV presents detailed use cases demonstrating the application of SSI across different industrial scenarios. Section V discusses integration strategies in mobile network environments and addresses compatibility challenges with legacy OT devices. Finally, Section VI concludes the paper by summarizing the benefits of SSI integration in industrial networks.

II. BACKGROUND, THREATS AND LOGICAL FRAMEWORK FOR INDUSTRIAL SYSTEMS

A. IACS Logical Framework

To understand the security and network system requirements of an Industrial Automated Control System (IACS), it is neces-

sary to use a logical framework that incorporates blockchain-based SSI to describe the functions and composition of an industrial system as given in Figure 1. The industrial control hierarchy, augmented by blockchain-based SSI, can divide devices and equipment into hierarchical functions while ensuring that all interactions are authenticated and secure. The logical industrial cybersecurity framework for industrial automation networks complemented with BCN-based SSI is given in [6]. *The industrial zone*, where critical IACS applications, devices and controls are located, benefits significantly from blockchain-based SSI.

A hierarchical model of an industrial control system is divided into different zones and levels that correspond to different functional areas and security requirements. This structure is often referred to as Purdue Enterprise Reference Architecture (PERA), which divides industrial systems into different zones to improve security and operational efficiency [5]. *The Enterprise Zone* includes Levels 4 and 5, which include the Site Business Planning and Logistics Network and the Enterprise Network, respectively. These layers are responsible for high-level business functions such as Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP), logistics and other IT-centric operations. This zone is critical to the strategic management of the entire industrial operation and ensures that business processes are aligned with production requirements. *The Industrial Demilitarized Zone (IDMZ)* serves as a buffer between the Enterprise Zone and the more sensitive operational layers below. The IDMZ provides a secure interface through which data and services can be exchanged between IT and OT environments without jeopardizing the security of industrial operations. *The industrial zone* is the place where the main production activities take place. It comprises Level 3, which focuses on production processes and control on site. This level manages plant-wide operations, including the monitoring and control of production processes. It is supported by the cell/area zone, which includes Level 2 (area control), Level 1 (basic control) and Level 0 (process). These levels correspond to increasingly granular control functions, ranging from supervisory level to direct control of machines and processes on the factory floor. *The cell/area zone* is critical to real-time operations and ensures that industrial processes run smoothly and efficiently.

The safety zone is dedicated to safety-critical functions. This zone ensures that all operations are carried out safely to protect both employees and the environment from potential industrial hazards. The integration of blockchain-based Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) into this architecture increases security in all these zones and levels. In the Enterprise Zone, SSI can protect the identities of users and devices interacting with business-critical applications and ensure that only authorized individuals can access sensitive data. In the demilitarized Industrial Zone, SSI can authenticate data exchanges between the IT and OT environments, ensuring that all transactions are verified and secure. In the Industrial Zone and Cell/Area Zone, SSI can be used to manage and authenticate the identities of all devices and controllers such as PLCs and HMIs. By ensuring that only authenticated and authorized devices can communicate within

these levels, SSI helps to prevent unauthorized access and potential cyber-attacks on critical operational processes. Finally, in the safety zone, SSI can play a crucial role in ensuring that all security-critical operations are carried out by verified personnel and verified devices to ensure the highest level of security. By implementing blockchain-based SSI in this architecture, organizations can create a more secure, resilient and efficient industrial control system where every interaction is authenticated and every identity is verified, reducing the risk of security breaches and operational disruptions.

By implementing clear logical segmentation and SSI, this zone ensures that all devices and interactions within the IACS network are secure and compliant with standards such as IEC 62443. The safety zone, which is located below the industrial zone, is also enhanced by SSI. It ensures that only verified units can interact with safety-critical systems, reducing the risk of accidents caused by unauthorized access. *The cell/area zone*, which forms the basis of the industrial automation architecture, supports important automation and control functions. Blockchain-based SSI ensures that all devices within this zone are authenticated, enabling secure real-time communication between sensors, actuators, controllers and other IACS devices. This zone corresponds to levels 0-2 of the Purdue model and is critical to maintaining smooth plant operations. *The Site Operations and Control Zone*, which is the highest level of the IACS network, also benefits from blockchain-based SSI. By ensuring that all applications and services are used by authenticated entities, SSI increases the security and integrity of the network. This zone, which is typically managed by IT staff, is closely aligned with standard IT technologies, making the integration of SSI a natural fit for securing industrial applications. *The Enterprise Zone*, home to traditional IT systems, now includes blockchain-based SSI to manage identity and access control more effectively. Although direct access to the IACS is typically not required, the implementation of SSI ensures that any interaction between the enterprise systems and the IACS is secure and authenticated to prevent unauthorized access and ensure the stability of industrial operations. *The Industrial DMZ*, which separates the corporate network from the operational area, is crucial for secure data exchange. By integrating blockchain-based SSI, the DMZ ensures that all data and service interactions are authenticated, reducing the risk of external threats to the IACS network. This layer of security is critical to maintaining the operational integrity of industrial environments.

III. BLOCKCHAIN-BASED SELF-SOVEREIGN IDENTITY FOR OT SYSTEMS

Blockchain-based SSI provides a decentralized and secure approach to identity management, offering significant advantages for OOT systems [7]. Traditional identity management systems rely on centralized authorities, creating single points of failure and vulnerability. In contrast, Blockchain-SSI allows OT systems to manage device and user identities autonomously, ensuring enhanced security, trust, and auditability. Benefits of Blockchain-SSI in OT are (i) Decentral-

Fig. 1: The Purdue Enterprise Reference Architecture (PERA) framework for an industrial automation network integrated with blockchain-based SSI around multiple zones

ized identity verification eliminates reliance on centralized servers, (ii) Tamper-proof identity records enhance trust and transparency, (iii) Immutable audit trails facilitate compliance with regulatory requirements, (iv) Improved scalability for managing large-scale OT networks with diverse devices [8].

IV. COMMON USE CASES

A. Use Case 1: Maintenance Workstations with Blockchain-based SSI

Figure 2 illustrates maintenance workstations that can be located within a cell/area zone or in a special zone outside the cell. These workstations often require elevated privileges when interacting with other zones [9]. By using blockchain-based SSI, the identity of the workstation and operator can be verified before cross-zone interactions take place. This ensures that only authorized maintenance activities are performed to protect critical infrastructure from unauthorized access.

B. Use Case 2: Interlocking Interzone communication with Blockchain-based SSI

As shown in Figure 3, to prevent the spread of malware, only certain industrial communications need to cross different zones for distributed automation functions, which is also in line with the principles of the Zero Trust Architecture (ZTA) [10]. Blockchain-based SSI can ensure that only verified PLCs and communication protocols are allowed to interact across zones, while maintaining a least privilege policy. This prevents unauthorized devices or malware from propagating across zones and secures the network against lateral movement and unauthorized access.

Fig. 2: Maintenance workstations may operate within or outside the cell zone, with elevated privileges secured by SSI.

Fig. 3: Select devices, such as interlocking PLCs, require secure cross-zone communication, managed with SSI.

C. Use Case 3: Convenience Port with Blockchain-based SSI

Operators often connect directly to the infrastructure by using convenience ports [6], as shown in Figure 4. With blockchain-based SSI, these ports can be secured by verifying the identity and device status of the user before granting access. This prevents unauthorized access and ensures that only authenticated users with compliant devices can connect to the network, maintaining the integrity and security of the system.

Fig. 4: Operators use convenience ports to access extra services, secured by SSI.

D. Use Case 4: Safety Networks with Blockchain-based SSI

Safety Instrumented Systems (SIS) are critical components of the control network [11]. As shown in Figure 5, blockchain-based SSI can be used to enforce strict identity verification for any entity attempting to interact with the SIS. Regardless of whether it is an air-gapped system or a logically segmented system [12], these systems require the highest level of security. SSI can provide an immutable record of all interactions and ensures that only authorized entities can access or control the SIS.

E. Use Case 5: Remote Users with Blockchain-based SSI

Remote access, which is often granted to employees, partners and vendors, requires strict access controls [13]. As shown in Figure 6, blockchain-based SSI can ensure that remote users are verified before they can interact with selected devices on the factory floor. Access is restricted to specific devices and for a limited time, reducing the risk of unauthorized access and ensuring that all remote interactions are secure and traceable. To summarize, a robust and flexible network architecture is essential to achieve certified security. The integration of blockchain-based SSI improves the network design by ensuring that all interactions are authenticated and secure. This is particularly important in the cell/area zone, operation and control zone and IDMZ, where SSI ensures that only verified entities can interact with the network, reducing the risk of unauthorized access and potential security breaches.

Finally, Table I provides a summary of the studied use cases for blockchain-based SSI in industrial networks.

Fig. 5: Safety Networks are either air-gapped or logically separated, with access controlled by SSI.

V. BLOCKCHAIN-BASED SSI INTEGRATION FOR OT SECURITY IN MOBILE NETWORKS

The integration of OT systems into mobile network environments, especially in 5G and beyond, can bring new challenges in securing communications, devices and identities. Traditional identity management systems are often based on centralized architectures that are prone to single points of failure, scaling issues and insufficient data protection. A blockchain-based SSI framework offers a decentralized and secure alternative to improve OT security in mobile networks and enable efficient identity management while eliminating these vulnerabilities.

A. Integration Scenarios

(i) *Secure Device Onboarding in 5G Networks:* When new OT devices, such as IoT sensors or power controllers, are deployed in mobile networks, secure onboarding is critical. Blockchain-based SSI enables these devices to set up decentralized identifiers (DIDs) that are connected to the network's blockchain infrastructure. During onboarding, a device generates its own DID and stores it in the blockchain. Network operators issue verifiable credentials, such as certificates of compliance, which are anchored in the DID. Other devices and systems within the network can verify these credentials without relying on a central authority.

(ii) *Enhancing Access Control for OT Systems:* Access control in OT systems often requires verification of user or system identities to prevent unauthorized changes to critical configurations. SSI can improve access control in mobile networks by (i) issuing role-specific credentials (e.g. operator, administrator) linked to user DIDs (ii) allowing OT systems to verify these credentials via the blockchain without querying a central server. (iii) Dynamically update or revoke credentials when roles or permissions change.

(iii) *Securing Remote Monitoring and Control:* Remote monitoring systems in OT environments transmit sensitive

Fig. 6: Remote users require restricted access to select devices, secured by SSI.

TABLE I: Blockchain-based SSI Use Cases in Industrial Networks

Use Case	Pros with Blockchain Systems	Cons with Blockchain Systems	Additional Considerations	Addressing Drawbacks
Maintenance Workstations [9]	Verifies identity before allowing cross-zone access, protecting critical infrastructure. Prevents unauthorized modifications.	Increased authentication time may delay urgent tasks. Requires ongoing cryptographic management.	Ensures maintenance activities are performed securely, minimizing risks to critical infrastructure.	Pre-configure access permissions for emergency scenarios to reduce delays.
Interlocking inter-zone communication [10]	Secure cross-zone communication ensures integrity of distributed automation systems. Prevents lateral movement of malware.	Increased complexity in managing cross-zone communications. Potential delays in system processes.	Protects distributed automation processes from cross-zone breaches and unauthorized access.	Implement automated trust policies to ease management of cross-zone communications.
Convenience Ports [6]	Verifies identity and device compliance before granting access. Secures convenience ports from unauthorized use.	Slight delays in port access times due to verification. May require additional hardware for compliance checks.	Safeguards access for technicians or operators using convenience ports, ensuring network security.	Optimize device verification processes to reduce port access delays while maintaining security.
Safety Networks [11]	Strict verification ensures only authorized entities interact with Safety Instrumented Systems (SIS). Immutable record of all interactions.	Complexity in managing air-gapped systems. High computational cost for large-scale deployments.	Protects life-critical safety processes from unauthorized access or interference, enhancing operational safety.	Apply optimized blockchain protocols designed for air-gapped and resource-limited systems.
Remote Users [13]	Verifies remote user identities and restricts access to specific devices. Limits access time to reduce risks.	Potential delays in remote access verification. Requires robust remote credential management.	Adds traceability and restriction for remote access, ensuring only legitimate users can interact with critical systems.	Use temporary access tokens to balance security and access speed for remote users.

data that must be protected from tampering. SSI ensures secure communication by (i) Attaching verifiable credentials to each OT device certifying its authenticity and operational status (ii) Using blockchain to log and validate control commands, creating a tamper-proof audit trail for traceability. (iii) Enabling zero-trust architectures where every interaction is independently authenticated.

B. General Workflow for OT with Blockchain-SSI Integration

The integration of Blockchain-SSI in OT introduces a new workflow for managing device and user identities. The following steps outline the process: (i) *Identity Registration*: Devices and users are registered on the blockchain using cryptographically secure identities. These identities are issued by a trusted authority or derived from device-specific characteristics. (ii) *Identity Verification*: When accessing OT systems, users and devices present verifiable credentials (VCs) stored on the blockchain. Smart contracts validate these credentials without requiring a centralized server. (iii) *Authentication and Authorization*: Based on verified credentials, the blockchain enforces role-based access control, ensuring least-privilege access. (iv) *Continuous Monitoring and Revocation*: The blockchain maintains an immutable audit trail of identity activities. Revocation of credentials is performed transparently

and instantly propagated across the network. (v) *Audit and Compliance*: Blockchain-based logs provide verifiable proof of access and identity-related activities for regulatory and security audits.

C. Compatibility of SSI with ICS/OT Devices

The compatibility of SSI with ICS/OT devices largely depends on the specific implementation of SSI and the computational capabilities of the devices. Some key factors related to this compatibility are as follows:

D. ICS/OT Device Constraints

Many OT devices are legacy systems with limited computational power, memory, and storage. These devices were not designed for modern cryptographic operations or protocols. OT systems often operate in real-time, meaning that delays caused by computational overhead could disrupt critical operations. Devices in OT environments, especially those in remote or hazardous areas, are often energy-constrained and rely on lightweight processing.

E. SSI Computational Requirements

The generation and management of DIDs are computationally lightweight and should be compatible with most OT devices. The creation, signing, and verification of VCs involve

cryptographic operations. While modern asymmetric cryptography (e.g., RSA or ECC) is efficient, resource-constrained OT devices may struggle with these operations. If SSI is integrated with blockchain, additional computational and networking overhead is introduced, including maintaining blockchain connectivity and processing smart contracts. Transitioning to PQC for quantum-safe SSI introduces even greater computational requirements due to the more complex algorithms.

F. Mitigation Strategies for Compatibility

To ensure compatibility of SSI with ICS/OT devices, the following strategies can be employed: (i) Use *gateways* or *edge devices* to handle heavy cryptographic operations, such as VC signing and blockchain interactions, offloading the burden from OT devices. (ii) Employ lightweight cryptographic algorithms that meet the security requirements of SSI while being computationally efficient (e.g., symmetric cryptography for local operations). (iii) Combine traditional identity mechanisms for resource-constrained devices with SSI for more capable components of the OT network. (iv) Restrict full SSI adoption to devices with sufficient computational power while leveraging proxies or adapters for less capable devices. (v) Adapt SSI frameworks for OT environments, prioritizing computational efficiency and minimal resource use.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have explored the integration of blockchain-based SSI into IACS to address evolving security challenges. By leveraging SSI, industrial systems can create a robust framework for authentication, authorization and secure communication that mitigates the threats and vulnerabilities of traditional identity management systems. We have presented a logical framework for a layered defense, highlighting the adaptability and scalability of blockchain-based SSI in complex industrial environments. Using detailed use cases, we demonstrated the practical application of SSI in various scenarios, including maintenance workstations, interzone communications, convenience ports, security networks and remote access by authorized users. These use cases illustrate the versatility and efficiency gains that can be achieved with SSI while improving the security of industrial operations.

The introduction of blockchain-based SSIs within IACS offers transformative potential, not only in terms of improving security, but also in terms of promoting trust, reducing administrative burden and ensuring compliance with new regulatory standards. As industrial systems continue to evolve and integrate with advanced digital technologies, SSI is an important cornerstone for creating secure, autonomous and resilient industrial ecosystems. As SSI frameworks evolve, and with the development of energy-efficient cryptographic hardware and software optimizations, compatibility with ICS/OT devices is expected to improve significantly. However, legacy devices may still require specialized solutions or upgrades. Future work could explore the interoperability of blockchain-based SSI with legacy systems, its scalability in large-scale industrial deployments, and the economic impact of widespread

adoption. In addition, further research into the integration of SSI with other emerging technologies, such as post-quantum security, could open up new opportunities to improve the security and functionality of industrial systems [14].

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